

LIST OF REFERENCES

The literature references used for the data collection and analysis were taken from: Djokic *et al.*, 2023. doi: [10.1080/22221751.2023.2249126](https://doi.org/10.1080/22221751.2023.2249126):

[1] Day MJ. Cats are not small dogs: is there an immunological explanation for why cats are less affected by arthropod-borne disease than dogs? *Parasit Vectors*. 2016/09/21 ed. 2016;9:507.

[2] HCSP. Avis relatif à la conduite à tenir vis-à-vis de personnes exposées à des animaux contaminés par *Brucella canis*. publique HC de la santé, editor. 2022; Available from: https://www.hcsp.fr/Explore.cgi/Telecharger?NomFichier=hcspa20220318_cotevividepeexdeanatdebrca.pdf.

[3] HAIRS members and external experts. Risk review and statement on the risk *Brucella canis* presents to the UK human population [Internet]. HAIRS; 2021. Available from: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/960013/20210210_Brucella_canis_statement.pdf.

[4] Celli J. The Intracellular Life Cycle of *Brucella* spp. *Microbiol Spectr* [Internet]. 2019/03/09 ed. 2019;7. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/30848234>.

- [5] Roop RM 2nd, Barton IS, Hoppersberger D, et al. Uncovering the Hidden Credentials of Brucella Virulence. *Microbiol Mol Biol Rev.* 2021/02/12 ed. 2021;85.
- [6] Stranahan LW, Arenas-Gamboa AM. When the Going Gets Rough: The Significance of Brucella Lipopolysaccharide Phenotype in Host-Pathogen Interactions. *Front Microbiol.* 2021/08/03 ed. 2021;12:713157.
- [7] Fernández AG, Hielpos MS, Ferrero MC, et al. Proinflammatory response of canine trophoblasts to Brucella canis infection. *PLOS ONE.* 2017;12:e0186561.
- [8] Ahmed W, Zheng K, Liu ZF. Establishment of Chronic Infection: Brucella's Stealth Strategy. *Front Cell Infect Microbiol.* 2016/03/26 ed. 2016;6:30.
- [9] Bin Park W, Kim S, Kyung SM, et al. Gene expression of Toll-like receptors, cytokines and a nuclear factor and cytokine secretion in DH82 canine macrophage cells infected with Brucella canis. *Vet Immunol Immunopathol.* 2023;260:110607.
- [10] Lucero NE, Corazza R, Almuzara MN, et al. Human Brucella canis outbreak linked to infection in dogs. *Epidemiol Infect.* 2009/08/06 ed. 2010;138:280–285.
- [11] Hensel ME, Negron M, Arenas-Gamboa AM. Brucellosis in Dogs and Public Health Risk. *Emerg Infect Dis.* 2018/07/18 ed. 2018;24:1401–1406.
- [12] Carmichael LE, Joubert JC. Transmission of Brucella canis by contact exposure. *Cornell Vet.* 1988/01/01 ed. 1988;78:63–73.
- [13] De Massis F, Sacchini F, Averaimo D, et al. First Isolation of Brucella canis from a breeding kennel in Italy. *Vet Ital.* 2021/10/14 ed. 2021;57:3.
- [14] Ferreira Vicente A, Girault G, Corde Y, et al. New insights into phylogeography of worldwide Brucella canis isolates by comparative genomics-based approaches: focus on Brazil. *BMC Genomics.* 2018/08/30 ed. 2018;19:636.
- [15] Keid LB, Chiebao DP, Batinga MCA, et al. Brucella canis infection in dogs from commercial breeding kennels in Brazil. *Transbound Emerg Dis.* 2017/03/16 ed. 2017;64:691–697.
- [16] Buhmann G, Paul F, Herbst W, et al. Canine Brucellosis: Insights Into the Epidemiologic Situation in Europe. *Front Vet Sci.* 2019/06/20 ed. 2019;6:151.
- [17] Whatmore, Perrett, Friggens. Second UK isolation of Brucella canis. *Vet Rec.* 2017;180:617.

[18] Egloff S, Schneeberger M, Gobeli S, et al. Brucella canis infection in a young dog with epididymitis and orchitis. Schweiz Arch Tierheilkd. 2018/12/06 ed. 2018;160:743–748.

[19] van Dijk MAM, Engelsma MY, Visser VXN, et al. Transboundary Spread of Brucella canis through Import of Infected Dogs, the Netherlands, November 2016–December 2018. Emerg Infect Dis. 2021/06/22 ed. 2021;27:1783–1788.

[20] AHMET MURAT SAYTEKİN MSK BUKET ALTUNTAŞ, GÜLSEREN YILDIZ ÖZ, GÜLNAZ MECİTOĞLU, ÖZGE YILMAZ. The first-time isolation of Brucella canis from two aborted bitches in a kennel in Turkey. Turk J Vet Anim Sci. 2018;42:3.

[21] Rossow H, JS Tuominen P. Zoonotic pathogens in imported dogs. Oksanen A, NA Jokelainen P, Heikinheimo A, Grönthal T, Tamminen T, Skrzypczak T, Rimhanen-Finne R, Nokireki T, Haikka S, Hakkarainen T, Viitasaari E, Valle V and Ruotsalainen E, editor. 2019; Available from: https://www.ruokavirasto.fi/globalassets/tietoa-meista/julkaisut/julkaisusarjat/tutkimukset/riskiraportit/2019_2_zoonoottiset-taudinaiheuttajat-tuontikoirissa.pdf.

[22] Corrente M, Franchini D, Decaro N, et al. Detection of Brucella canis in a dog in Italy. New Microbiol. 2011/01/11 ed. 2010;33:337–341.

[23] Morgan, Rys, Wake, et al. Brucella canis in a dog in the UK. Vet Rec. 2017;180:384–385.

[24] Holst BS, Lofqvist K, Ernholm L, et al. The first case of Brucella canis in Sweden: background, case report and recommendations from a northern European perspective. Acta Vet Scand. 2012/03/29 ed. 2012;54:18.

[25] Kaden R, Agren J, Ferrari S, et al. Whole-Genome Sequence of Brucella canis Strain SVA13, Isolated from an Infected Dog. Genome Announc [Internet]. 2014/07/19 ed. 2014;2. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/25035330>.

[26] Dentinger CM, Jacob K, Lee LV, et al. Human Brucella canis Infection and Subsequent Laboratory Exposures Associated with a Puppy, New York City, 2012. Zoonoses Public Health. 2014/11/05 ed. 2015;62:407–414.

[27] Kolwijck E, Lutgens SP, Visser VX, et al. First case of human Brucella canis infection in the Netherlands. Clin Infect Dis [Internet]. 2022/06/03 ed. 2022; Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/35653425>.

IDEMBRU is a part of One Health European Joint Programme (EJP). This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

[28] Boyden P. Should we be doing more about *Brucella canis*? *Vet Rec.* 2022/07/23 ed. 2022;191:82.

[29] Ledbetter EC, Landry MP, Stokol T, et al. *Brucella canis* endophthalmitis in 3 dogs: clinical features, diagnosis, and treatment. *Vet Ophthalmol.* 2009/04/28 ed. 2009;12:183–191.

[30] Alton G.G., Jones L.M., Angus R.D., et al. *Techniques for the brucellosis laboratory.* Paris: INRA; 1988.

[31] Elbehiry A, Aldubaib M, Al Rugaie O, et al. Proteomics-based screening and antibiotic resistance assessment of clinical and sub-clinical *Brucella* species: An evolution of brucellosis infection control. *PloS One.* 2022;17:e0262551.

[32] Vila T, Nazir R, Rozental S, et al. The Role of Hydrophobicity and Surface Receptors at Hyphae of *Lyophyllum* sp. Strain Karsten in the Interaction with *Burkholderia terrae* BS001 - Implications for Interactions in Soil. *Front Microbiol.* 2016/11/12 ed. 2016;7:1689.

[33] Ferreira L, Vega Castano S, Sanchez-Juanes F, et al. Identification of *Brucella* by MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry. Fast and reliable identification from agar plates and blood cultures. *PLoS One.* 2010/12/15 ed. 2010;5:e14235.

[34] Scholz HC, Pfeffer M, Witte A, et al. Specific detection and differentiation of *Ochrobactrum anthropi*, *Ochrobactrum intermedium* and *Brucella* spp. by a multi-primer PCR that targets the *recA* gene. *J Med Microbiol.* 2007/12/11 ed. 2008;57:64–71.

[35] Bounaadja L, Albert D, Chénais B, et al. Real-time PCR for identification of *Brucella* spp.: A comparative study of IS711, *bcs*31 and *per* target genes. *Vet Microbiol.* 2009;137:156–164.

[36] Gopaul KK, Koylass MS, Smith CJ, et al. Rapid identification of *Brucella* isolates to the species level by real time PCR based single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) analysis. *BMC Microbiol.* 2008/06/04 ed. 2008;8:86.

[37] Lopez-Goni I, Garcia-Yoldi D, Marin CM, et al. New Bruce-ladder multiplex PCR assay for the biovar typing of *Brucella suis* and the discrimination of *Brucella suis* and *Brucella canis*. *Vet Microbiol.* 2011/07/26 ed. 2011;154:152–155.

IDEMBRU is a part of One Health European Joint Programme (EJP).
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

- [38] Girault G, Perrot L, Mick V, et al. High-Resolution Melting PCR as Rapid Genotyping Tool for Brucella Species. *Microorganisms* [Internet]. 2022/02/26 ed. 2022;10. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/35208791>.
- [39] Keid LB, Soares RM, Vasconcellos SA, et al. A polymerase chain reaction for detection of *Brucella canis* in vaginal swabs of naturally infected bitches. *Theriogenology*. 2007/10/09 ed. 2007;68:1260–1270.
- [40] Keid LB, Soares RM, Vieira NR, et al. Diagnosis of canine brucellosis: comparison between serological and microbiological tests and a PCR based on primers to 16S-23S rDNA interspacer. *Vet Res Commun*. 2007;31:951–965.
- [41] Boeri EJ, Wanke MM, Madariaga MJ, et al. Comparison of four polymerase chain reaction assays for the detection of *Brucella* spp. in clinical samples from dogs. *Vet World*. 2018/04/17 ed. 2018;11:201–208.
- [42] Keid LB, Soares RM, Vasconcellos SA, et al. Comparison of a PCR assay in whole blood and serum specimens for canine brucellosis diagnosis. *Vet Rec*. 2010/07/21 ed. 2010;167:96–99.
- [43] Batinga MCA, de Lima JTR, Gregori F, et al. Comparative application of IS711-based polymerase chain reaction (PCR) and loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP) for canine brucellosis diagnosis. *Mol Cell Probes*. 2018/03/11 ed. 2018;39:1–6.
- [44] Ashford R, Watmore. *Brucella*. *Mol Typing Bact Infect*. de Filippis. Springer International Publishing; 2022. p. 217–245.
- [45] Myers DM, Jones LM, Varela-Diaz VM. Studies of antigens for complement fixation and gel diffusion tests in the diagnosis of infections caused by *Brucella ovis* and other *Brucella*. *Appl Microbiol*. 1972/05/01 ed. 1972;23:894–902.
- [46] Badakhsh FF, Carmichael LE, Douglass JA. Improved rapid slide agglutination test for presumptive diagnosis of canine brucellosis. *J Clin Microbiol*. 1982;15:286–289.
- [47] Cortina ME, Novak A, Melli LJ, et al. Development of improved enzyme-based and lateral flow immunoassays for rapid and accurate serodiagnosis of canine brucellosis. *Vet Microbiol*. 2017;208:174–180.

- [48] Ducrotoy MJ, Muñoz PM, Conde-Álvarez R, et al. A systematic review of current immunological tests for the diagnosis of cattle brucellosis. *Prev Vet Med.* 2018/03/03 ed. 2018;151:57–72.
- [49] Santos RL, Souza TD, Mol JPS, et al. Canine Brucellosis: An Update. *Front Vet Sci.* 2021/03/20 ed. 2021;8:594291.
- [50] Carmichael. *Greene's Infectious Diseases of the Dog and Cat.* 5th edition. Saunders (24/06/2022); 2021.
- [51] de Souza TD, de Carvalho TF, Mol J, et al. Tissue distribution and cell tropism of *Brucella canis* in naturally infected canine foetuses and neonates. *Sci Rep.* 2018/05/10 ed. 2018;8:7203.
- [52] Falenski A, Mayer-Scholl A, Filter M, et al. Survival of *Brucella* spp. in mineral water, milk and yogurt. *Int J Food Microbiol.* 2010/12/21 ed. 2011;145:326–330.
- [53] Aune K, Rhyan JC, Russell R, et al. Environmental persistence of *Brucella abortus* in the Greater Yellowstone Area. *J Wildl Manag.* 2012;76:253–261.
- [54] Lucero NE, Maldonado PI, Kaufman S, et al. *Brucella canis* causing infection in an HIV-infected patient. *Vector Borne Zoonotic Dis.* 2009/09/04 ed. 2010;10:527–529.
- [55] Lawaczek E, Toporek J, Cwikla J, et al. *Brucella canis* in a HIV-infected patient. *Zoonoses Public Health.* 2011/02/11 ed. 2011;58:150–152.
- [56] Lucero NE, Escobar GI, Ayala SM, et al. Diagnosis of human brucellosis caused by *Brucella canis*. *J Med Microbiol.* 2005/04/13 ed. 2005;54:457–461.
- [57] Wallach JC, Giambartolomei GH, Baldi PC, et al. Human infection with M- strain of *Brucella canis*. *Emerg Infect Dis.* 2004/04/14 ed. 2004;10:146–148.
- [58] Pereira CR, Cotrim de Almeida JVF, Cardoso de Oliveira IR, et al. Occupational exposure to *Brucella* spp.: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis.* 2020/05/12 ed. 2020;14:e0008164.
- [59] Ahmed-Bentley J, Roman S, Mirzanejad Y, et al. Laboratory Exposures from an Unsuspected Case of Human Infection with *Brucella canis*. *Emerg Infect Dis.* 2021/08/24 ed. 2021;27:2489–2491.

[60] Viana MVC, Wattam AR, Govil Batra D, et al. Genome Sequences of Three *Brucella canis* Strains Isolated from Humans and a Dog. *Genome Announc*. 2017;5:e01688-16.

[61] Lum MK, Pien FD, Sasaki DM. Human *Brucella canis* infection in Hawaii. *Hawaii Med J*. 1985/02/01 ed. 1985;44:66, 68.

[62] Nomura A, Imaoka K, Imanishi H, et al. Human *Brucella canis* infections diagnosed by blood culture. *Emerg Infect Dis*. 2010/07/01 ed. 2010;16:1183–1185.

[63] Piao D, Wang H, Di D, et al. MLVA and LPS Characteristics of *Brucella canis* Isolated from Humans and Dogs in Zhejiang, China. *Front Vet Sci*. 2018/01/13 ed. 2017;4:223.

[64] Mohamed Zahidi J, Ahmad N, Tay BY, et al. Genome Sequences of *Brucella melitensis*, Isolated from Blood Samples of Brucellosis Patients in Malaysia. *Genome Announc* [Internet]. 2017/08/05 ed. 2017;5. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/28774972>.

[65] Schoenemann J, Lutticken R, Scheibner E. [*Brucella canis* infection in man]. *Dtsch Med Wochenschr*. 1986/01/03 ed. 1986;111:20–22.

[66] King J. Heartbroken woman forced to put five dogs down after contracting rare disease. *METRO UK* [Internet]. 2022 Aug 14; Available from: <https://metro.co.uk/2022/08/14/woman-forced-to-put-five-dogs-down-after-contracting-rare-disease-17180788/>.

[67] Blankenship RM, Sanford JP. *Brucella canis*. A cause of undulant fever. *Am J Med*. 1975/09/01 ed. 1975;59:424–426.

[68] Tosi MF, Nelson TJ. *Brucella canis* infection in a 17-month-old child successfully treated with moxalactam. *J Pediatr*. 1982/11/01 ed. 1982;101:725–727.

[69] McKee MA, Ballard JL. Mycotic aneurysms of the tibioperoneal arteries. *Ann Vasc Surg*. 1999/03/11 ed. 1999;13:188–190.

[70] Ying W, Nguyen MQ, Jahre JA. *Brucella canis* endocarditis: case report. *Clin Infect Dis*. 1999/12/10 ed. 1999;29:1593–1594.

[71] Laine C, Johnson V, Scott H, et al. Human brucellosis: First calculated estimate of global annual incidence. *Brucell 2022 Int Res Conf*. Terramo, Italy: IZSAM; 2022.

IDEMBRU is a part of One Health European Joint Programme (EJP). This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

[72] Eckstein C, Mol JPS, Costa FB, et al. *Brucella ovis* mutant in ABC transporter protects against *Brucella canis* infection in mice and it is safe for dogs. *PLoS One*. 2020/04/17 ed. 2020;15:e0231893.

[73] Kim WK, Moon JY, Cho JS, et al. *Brucella abortus* lysed cells using GI24 induce robust immune response and provide effective protection in Beagles. *Pathog Dis* [Internet]. 2017/12/23 ed. 2018;76. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/29272378>.

[74] Hollett RB. Canine brucellosis: outbreaks and compliance. *Theriogenology*. 2006/05/24 ed. 2006;66:575–587.

[75] Mateu-de-Antonio EM, Martin M. In vitro efficacy of several antimicrobial combinations against *Brucella canis* and *Brucella melitensis* strains isolated from dogs. *Vet Microbiol*. 1995/06/01 ed. 1995;45:1–10.

[76] De Massis F, Sacchini F, Petrini A, et al. Canine brucellosis due to *Brucella canis*: description of the disease and control measures. *Vet Ital*. 2022/06/30 ed. 2022;58:5–23.

[77] Guarino C, Franklin-Guild R, Goodrich E, et al. Antibody response over time correlated with treatment outcome in 30 dogs naturally infected with *Brucella canis* (2017–2022). *Am J Vet Res*. 2023;1:1–7.

[78] Wanke MM, Delpino MV, Baldi PC. Use of enrofloxacin in the treatment of canine brucellosis in a dog kennel (clinical trial). *Theriogenology*. 2006/02/16 ed. 2006;66:1573–1578.

[79] Liu Y, Sun J, Peng X, et al. Deletion of the LuxR-type regulator VjbR in *Brucella canis* affects expression of type IV secretion system and bacterial virulence, and the mutant strain confers protection against *Brucella canis* challenge in mice. *Microb Pathog*. 2019/11/13 ed. 2020;139:103865.

[80] Stranahan LW, Chaki SP, Garcia-Gonzalez DG, et al. Evaluation of the Efficacy of the *Brucella canis* RM6/66 DeltavjbR Vaccine Candidate for Protection against *B. canis* Infection in Mice. *mSphere* [Internet]. 2020/05/22 ed. 2020;5. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/32434839>.

[81] Keid LB, Diniz JA, Oliveira TM, et al. Evaluation of an Immunochromatographic Test to the Diagnosis of Canine Brucellosis Caused by *Brucella canis*. *Reprod Domest Anim*. 2015/10/23 ed. 2015;50:939–944.

IDEMBRU is a part of One Health European Joint Programme (EJP). This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

[82] Escobar GI, Boeri EJ, Ayala SM, et al. The feasibility of using antigens prepared with rough Brucella strains for diagnosis of canine brucellosis. *Rev Argent Microbiol.* 2010/05/13 ed. 2010;42:35–40.

[83] Wanke MM, Cairó F, Rossano M, et al. Preliminary study of an immunochromatography test for serological diagnosis of canine brucellosis. *Reprod Domest Anim Zuchthyg.* 2012;47 Suppl 6:370–372.

[84] Zoha SJ, Carmichael LE. Serological responses of dogs to cell wall and internal antigens of *Brucella canis* (*B. canis*). *Vet Microbiol.* 1982;7:35–50.

[85] Lucero NE, Escobar GI, Ayala SM, et al. Sensitivity and specificity of an indirect enzyme-linked immunoassay for the diagnosis of *Brucella canis* infection in dogs. *J Med Microbiol.* 2002/08/13 ed. 2002;51:656–660.

[86] de Oliveira MZ, Vale V, Keid L, et al. Validation of an ELISA method for the serological diagnosis of canine brucellosis due to *Brucella canis*. *Res Vet Sci.* 2010/08/10 ed. 2011;90:425–431.

[87] Kim JW, Lee YJ, Han MY, et al. Evaluation of immunochromatographic assay for serodiagnosis of *Brucella canis*. *J Vet Med Sci.* 2007/12/07 ed. 2007;69:1103–1107.

[88] Carmichael LE, Joubert JC. A rapid slide agglutination test for the serodiagnosis of *Brucella canis* infection that employs a variant (M-) organism as antigen. *Cornell Vet.* 1987;77:3–12.

[89] Keid LB, Soares RM, Vasconcellos SA, et al. Comparison of agar gel immunodiffusion test, rapid slide agglutination test, microbiological culture and PCR for the diagnosis of canine brucellosis. *Res Vet Sci.* 2009;86:22–26.

[90] Baldi PC, Wanke MM, Loza ME, et al. *Brucella abortus* cytoplasmic proteins used as antigens in an ELISA potentially useful for the diagnosis of canine brucellosis. *Vet Microbiol.* 1994/07/01 ed. 1994;41:127–134.

[91] Baldi PC, Wanke MM, Loza ME, et al. Diagnosis of canine brucellosis by detection of serum antibodies against an 18 kDa cytoplasmic protein of *Brucella* spp. *Vet Microbiol.* 1997;57:273–281.

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